

A systematic literature review on the effect of municipal mergers

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Abstract: This paper systematically reviews the international empirical literature on the effects of municipal mergers. We clarify current research priorities and new research extensions and identify consensus and controversy in existing research. Our findings show that the number of papers on municipal merger research increased in recent years. In terms of economic effects, most studies observe that although municipal mergers will significantly reduce administrative expenditures, they will not likewise significantly reduce the total expenditure of local governments. In terms of democratic effects, municipal mergers have significant adverse effects. On the one hand, the expansion of jurisdictions increases the political and physical distance between voters and politicians, whilst voters have a lower sense of local identity; on the other hand, it becomes more difficult for governments in large jurisdictions to satisfy heterogeneous preferences. In terms of management effects, municipal mergers usually do not improve public services and administrative efficiency but make efforts to create a vision, serve the mayor, and maintain external relations. Methodologically, we emphasize the identification of endogeneity issues and causality, and the difference-in-differences method is most frequently used. Finally, we propose future research priorities and areas that may need attention and propose a series of policy recommendations from the perspectives of central and local governments.

Keywords: Municipal merger; Literature review; Local governments; Common Pool; Democratic participation; Economic performance

JEL classification: H11; H77; H83; P11; R58

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1 Introduction

Municipal mergers are a universal phenomenon in the world. Since World War II, developed and developing countries have implemented municipal mergers of varying degrees. The United States has a long historical tradition in the reform of city-county mergers. Especially after the Great Depression in the United States, city-county mergers were increasingly considered (Stenberg, 2011). Since the 1815 merger of New Orleans and New Orleans Parish became the first city-county merger case, in the following nearly 200 years, local governments in the United States have made about 166 attempts and successfully implemented 39 city-county merger reforms (Martin & Schiff, 2011). Hall et al. (2020) updated the number of successful cases to 41 and argued that attempts at city-county mergers are still popular with local governments. According to Swianiewicz (2018), 15 European countries implemented municipal reforms from 2008-2017, although the current territorial restructuring reform has become one of the most challenging reforms in the field of political reform. The merger policy has led to a reduction of over 5,000 European municipalities. However, the increase in municipality size raises concerns about diseconomies of scale, as an increased size may increase expenditures such as agency and information costs (Allers & Geertsema, 2016). The study of municipal mergers, including their motives and effects, has always been a classic and widely debated proposition in political science, economics, public administration, and geography. In the current article, we conduct a systematic review of empirical papers on the effect of municipal mergers over the past few decades, analyzing their number of publications, case distribution, research areas, consensus and controversy of results, and research methods. Finally, this study aims to point out the future research trends of municipal mergers and provide a reference for local governments to conduct policy evaluations.

Municipal merger research shows mixed evidence, with studies suggesting that municipal mergers reduce local government spending (Reingewertz, 2012), while others argue that municipal mergers increase local government spending (Miyazaki, 2018). Additionally, the controversy surrounding municipal merger reform is that it is tough to judge the all-around performance of reform. For example, the reform of municipal mergers is usually regarded as an effective way to realize economies of scale in local public services. Still, establishing a big government also alienates the distance between voters and politicians and has adverse democratic effects (Reingewertz & Serritzlew, 2019). The trade-off between economic and democratic effects has always been a classic problem in political science research (Blom-Hansen et al., 2014).

Compared with previous literature reviews on municipal mergers, the contributions of the present paper are fourfold. First, the latest empirical research literature has been added to the analysis in this paper. Many local government reform practices have caused scholars to pay great attention to municipal mergers. Given the rapid increase in the number of empirical papers on the effects of municipal mergers, our review work has been further expanded and supported by the corresponding literature. Second, we compare and analyze the research trends in developed and developing countries and summarize the specific research focuses of existing research in the three fields of economy, democracy, and management. Compared with developed countries, empirical research on developing countries is less and more concentrated in the field of local economic growth (Tang & Hewings, 2017). Comparative and inductive analysis help provide a close and detailed reference for different countries to make policy decisions. Third, based on the majority of empirical

results, we give a preliminary conclusion on the impact of municipal mergers in the fields of economy, democracy, and management. Municipal mergers do not reduce local government spending; at least this reduction is premised, but it expands the common pool size. Municipal mergers have a negative impact on democratic participation. The effects of municipal mergers on economic growth and public services are highly heterogeneous, and more empirical evidence is needed. For the heterogeneous results, we propose possible explanations in terms of the institutional context of the study, variable selection, data sources, and research methods. Fourth, we further discuss methodological issues.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 presents the selection criteria for the literary analysis in this paper. Section 3 provides a descriptive analysis of the sample literature. Section 4 summarizes the existing research's field classification, consensus, and controversies. Section 5 analyzes the possible reasons for the controversy and the understanding of the methodology. Section 6 concludes the paper with policy advice and proposes future research trends.

2 Search strategy and selection criteria

This paper sorts out the existing empirical evidence on the impact of municipal mergers. Our search platform is fully based on the Web of Science (WoS) database. In order to include all relevant papers, we refer to the commonly used expressions of municipal mergers and lock the search keywords in "local government amalgamations", "local government consolidations", "local government mergers", "local government annexations", "city-county amalgamations", "city-county consolidations", "city-county mergers", "city-county annexations", "municipal amalgamations", "municipal consolidations", "municipal mergers", "municipal annexations" and "administrative division adjustment". To facilitate international comparisons, we limited our search to papers published in English-language peer-reviewed journals. The starting time is the default setting of the WoS database, and we did not specify a start time. We searched in August 2022 and returned 199 relevant documents. Through the manual reading of the above literature (see Figure 1), we filtered out the articles that (1) Without assessing policy effect or theory only (113 papers), (2) Single-sector or village-scale consolidation (8 papers), and (3) Pre-assessment (9 papers). Using qualitative or quantitative methods, our empirical articles can be based on diverse data (such as statistics, questionnaires, and interviews). Also, we obtained 20 relevant pieces of literature by the snowball method. Finally, 89 empirical papers on the performance analysis of municipal mergers are accepted. Our analysis in the following sections relies on these papers.

Fig.1 Selection criteria

3 Descriptive analysis of sample literature

This section introduces the distribution of publication years, research areas, and topics to understand the sample literature. In the next section, we will conduct an in-depth analysis of the literature for each research area. Limited by the article's length, we present the specific descriptive analysis results in the appendix. We mainly find that the research literature on municipal mergers has increased significantly in recent years, most of which are from western developed countries. The current empirical analysis literature mainly focuses on the following three types of research areas: economic effects, democratic effects, and management effects. From a method perspective, the DID model is the most widely used in all research topics.

In the following analysis, we will focus on the above three research areas and their respective specific topics to expound the consensus and divergence of current empirical research.

4 Results: consensus and controversy

In this section, we will analyze the existing empirical articles according to the specific topics in each research field in Table 1, including the research area, research methods, research conclusions, and other considerations. At the end of each topic, we will give a conclusive summary. This section enables us to understand the prevailing conclusions about municipal mergers on different issues and provides support for analyzing existing research controversies in the next section.

4.1 Economic effects

We define the economic effect as the impact of municipal merger reform on local government spending, regional economic growth (e.g., GDP, income, employment, housing prices, and firms), and population migration. First, we propose the possible impact of municipal mergers on various issues based on a theoretical analysis of existing literature. Second, we show supporting evidence from the existing empirical literature. Finally, we provide an overall assessment of the impact of municipal mergers on various issues.

4.1.1 Local government spending

Assumptions. Economies of scale are the most common reason cited by proponents of municipal mergers (Reingewertz & Serritzlew, 2019). Those in power hope to save local government spending through the economies of scale created by municipal mergers. It is generally believed that large cities can rely on their size and specialization advantages to make long-term average production costs fall as output increases (McQuestin et al., 2022). Some scholars further pointed out that not all services in large cities have the potential for economies of scale. Capital-intensive services represented by urban infrastructure have good potential for economies of scale. In contrast, labor-intensive services directly related to citizens are usually more minor and more effective at scale (Bird & Slack, 1993). In addition, when the scale reaches a certain level, because the production process may face challenges such as congestion, pollution, coordination difficulties, etc., the benefits of scale will continue to decrease, and there may be diseconomies of scale (Cobban, 2019). We also need to note that from an organizational point of view, municipal mergers restructure the pre-merger independent municipal system, which may lead to changes in the number of agencies and administrative employees in the process, which also has important implications for local government administrative expenditures impact (Cobban, 2019).

Evidence base. Based on the above assumptions, existing empirical conclusions on the impact of municipal mergers on local government spending are also quite different. A total of 19 empirical papers (involving 12 countries) on the topic of local government spending are reviewed in this section, and the practical conclusions of these papers vary widely. A few scholars have concluded that municipal mergers can bring savings effects. Reingewertz's (2012) study on municipal mergers in Israel found that merger reforms resulted in a reduction in municipal spending of about 9% and found no evidence of a reduction in the level of service provided to residents of merged cities. Cobban (2019) used the difference-in-differences method to study Ontario (Canada), showing that local governments can gain economies of scale and reduce administration costs through consolidation.

More scholars observe that municipal mergers cannot reduce local government spending and may even increase spending. Nelson (1992) analyzed the impact of municipal mergers in Sweden using ordinary least squares regression. He found that mergers reduced competition among municipalities, thereby increasing the influence of institutional factors on local budgets and promoting the growth of the municipal public sector. Moisio and Uusitalo (2013) used the PSM model to study the impact of Finnish municipal mergers on local government expenditures and found that mergers increased the growth of most categories of expenditures, only reduced general administrative category expenditures, and the decline was much smaller than the growth of other categories of expenditures. The increase in spending may be due to transitional costs, such as acquiring new technology, renovating existing facilities, and aligning wages and salaries upwards. Aulich et al. (2014), through a case study of Australian municipal mergers and interviews with senior practitioners in local government departments, argue that integration does not lead to economies of scale. However, integrating more prominent local authorities helps improve the author's strategic capabilities. Blom-Hansen et al. (2016) used a difference-in-differences model to analyze the impact of Denmark's 2007 municipal reforms on government spending. The results showed that consolidation had no systematic effect on spending because cost savings in some areas

were offset by deterioration in other areas. For most public services, the size of the jurisdiction does not matter at all. Drew et al. (2016) compared the economies of scale of local governments in two years before and after the reform of municipal mergers in Queensland (Australia, 2006 and 2009). They found that 8% of the city councils (10 municipal councils, accounting for 64% of the Queensland population) were in the diseconomies of scale segment before the reform. Still, after the reform, this number increased to a quarter (13 city councils). Roesel (2017) used the synthetic control method to analyze the impact of municipal mergers in Saxony (Germany) on local government spending, and the results showed that mergers did not bring about a reduction in total spending, nor did they show a decrease in spending on administration, education, and social care. There appear to be no economies of scale in jurisdictions with more than 100,000 residents. Miyazaki (2018) used an instrumental variable approach to study municipal consolidation reforms in Japan and found that consolidation significantly increased per capita spending. Moreover, municipal spending increased immediately after consolidation but gradually declined. Research by Blesse and Roesel (2019) based on a difference-in-differences model shows that whether the county acts as a higher-level autonomous unit of local government (Germany) or as a branch of the state government (Austria), municipal mergers do not generate economies of scale and reduce local government expenditure. Harjunen et al. (2021) used a difference-in-differences model to study municipal mergers in Finland and found that mergers had no significant impact on total municipal expenses during the 8-year tracking period after the merger.

Some scholars also observe that the merger's expenditure reduction effect has specific conditions. Edwards and Xiao (2009) studied the impact of administrative mergers on per capita local government spending in the United States, arguing that spending is affected by mergers. Furthermore, this effect is moderated by population density. If higher population densities accompany mergers, local governments' level of per capita spending will undoubtedly fall. However, this saving effect disappears if lower population densities accompany mergers. Hanes (2015), based on empirical research in Sweden, found that municipal reforms in 1952 hurt per capita spending growth in merged cities from 1953 to 1959, but the interaction coefficient with population size suggests that this negative effect is moderated by population size. This means that a newly formed municipality, consisting of many small towns of the same size, can achieve economies of scale more easily after reform than by combining large and small cities. Based on a difference-in-differences model, Andrews (2015) found that the British merger reform only significantly reduced per capita administrative expenditure but had no significant impact on total and other types of expenditure. Blesse and Baskaran (2016) used a difference-in-differences model to study the German state of Brandenburg and found that municipal mergers can significantly reduce the administrative expenditure of local governments. This reduction mainly comes from forced merger reforms, and voluntary mergers do not result in spending cuts. However, the impact on total expenditure and the current expenditure is insignificant. Based on a difference-in-differences model, Allers and Geertsema (2016) found that municipal mergers in the Netherlands can reduce administrative expenditures but have no significant impact on total expenditures. Neither jurisdiction size, preference heterogeneity, nor the number of merged cities affects the effect of mergers on total spending. Mughan's (2019) study of Australia using a difference-in-differences model found that voluntary mergers led to a 10% decline in total per capita spending. Still, mandatory mergers failed to reduce spending; on average, the results were insignificant. Pickering et al. (2020) used nighttime light data and a difference-in-differences model to study the impact of Japan's municipal merger

reform on local government spending. They found that post-merger politicians may allocate more public spending to more populated areas. Less public expenditure is given to less populated areas of the combined city to maximize their re-election chances. McQuestin et al. (2022) used a difference-in-differences model to study the municipal merger reform in Queensland (Australia) in 2008. They found that the effect of the merger on local government spending was time-dependent, with initial savings offset by medium-term cost increases and, ultimately, long-term effects negligible.

Summary. Summarizing the above analysis, we find that the current mainstream view is that the merger will not directly reduce local government spending, and even if it does, it is conditional. This conditionality may be an important reason for the controversial conclusions of the study, and it is also essential for local governments in different countries to consider when specifying municipal merger policies, which we will discuss in Section 5.

4.1.2 Common pool

Assumptions. Unlike the discussion of post-consolidation subnational government spending in the previous section, the common pool highlights changes in individual subnational governments' expenditure (or debt) before the merger. Specifically, mergers create a pool of future commons that merged municipalities can try to tap before merging since they will not bear the total cost of their decisions (Hansen, 2019). Also, smaller old towns have a powerful incentive to use the communal pool since they can spread the cost of their "irrational" actions among the larger group. This logic has been called "exploitation of the great by the small" (Olson 1971). Besides, "the law of 1/n" states that as the number of groups increases, any one group bears a smaller share of project costs because projects are paid for from a "common pool" (Weingast et al., 1981). In conclusion, there is reason to believe that old local governments are incentivized to consume before closing time (Blom-Hansen, 2010).

Evidence base. This section examines 12 empirical papers (involving seven countries) related to the common pool issue, and the practical conclusions of these papers are consistent. Hinnerich (2009) used a difference-in-differences model to study the free-rider effect caused by Sweden's 1969-1974 municipal merger reforms and found that the reforms gave local governments an incentive to accumulate debt before mergers, as the new local taxpayers would share the cost. The strength of the free-rider encouragement depends on the population size of the initial area relative to the new site. Blom-Hansen (2010) analyzed the impact of Denmark's 2007 merger on the common pool based on ordinary least squares regression and found that the merger significantly expanded the size of the common pool. Jordahl and Liang (2010) also used a difference-in-differences model and found that the 1952 Swedish municipal merger reform significantly increased local government debt between 1948 and 1952. Hansen (2014) used a difference-in-differences model to study municipal spending in Denmark from 1996 to 2006 and showed that the pre-merger project size increases with the common pool. In the last year of the treatment period, the availability and size of the common pool had a positive and significant effect. Saarimaa and Tukiainen (2015) used per capita debt stock and cash reserves to test the free-riding hypothesis and found that free-riding behavior is expected in voluntary and forced mergers. The municipality did not lower local income tax rates or hire new staff. Common pool funds are primarily used for new investments and current spending. Hirota and

Yunoue (2017) used the PSM-DID model for municipal mergers in Japan and found that merged municipalities increased local government spending and bonds before the merger. Subordinate merging partners primarily cause this financial common pool problem. The dominant merger partners did not impose additional financial burdens before the union because they knew they would have more responsibilities after the merger. Nakazaw (2018) used a difference-in-differences model to find that reforming municipal mergers in Japan provided municipalities with free-riding incentives. Still, relevant laws and regulations can well restrict free-riding behavior.

Hansen's (2019) empirical study on municipal mergers in Denmark found that municipal budget overruns increase systematically as mutual funds expand, but only in municipalities where the mayor has not been re-elected as mayor of the newly merged municipality. The common pool size does not affect budget overruns in cities where the mayor is re-elected. Fritz and Feld (2020) studied the development of public pools for large-scale municipal mergers in Baden-Württemberg (Germany) in the early 1970s, arguing that merged municipalities will accelerate debt accumulation compared to unincorporated cities. This common pool development will be more intense if more municipalities are involved and when municipalities are merged using annexation. Hirota and Yunoue (2020) further analyzed the types of public investments that lead to fiscal common pool problems based on previous research on municipal mergers in Japan. They found that subordinate merger partners created fiscal common pool problems by increasing road and park construction before unions. Askim and Houlberg (2022) used micro-survey data to study the moderating effect of social norms on government overspending before the municipal merger reform in Norway. Their conclusions acknowledged the common pool problem and argued that officials' cognitions play a heterogeneous and vital role.

However, there are still a few heterogeneous conclusions. Based on South African empirical research, Goto et al. (2021) found that the South African municipalities reduced the number of borrowings before the merger, which may be due to the monitoring effect of the relevant departments. This result contradicts previous research suggesting that appropriate municipal merger policies can prevent fiscal common pool problems caused by free-rider behavior. According to the authors, their study is the first to demonstrate a reduction in borrowing before municipal mergers.

Summary. From the conclusions of most studies, we found that the research on the common pool problem has a relatively consistent decision; that is, municipal mergers will increase the common pool's size, and there will be opportunistic behavior. Especially in municipalities that are small or whose mayors cannot be re-elected, there is a solid free-rider incentive. However, research in South Africa shows that legal or other monitoring measures can effectively reduce the size of the common pool.

4.1.3 Economic growth

Assumptions. In this section, the economic growth we discuss mainly refers to the effects of municipal mergers on local GDP, taxation, resident income, employment, housing price, and enterprise development. However, not many theories show that municipal mergers boost economic growth. Some empirical studies show that municipal mergers can promote regional economic development through agglomeration economies (Tang & Hewings, 2017). Therefore, the empirical conclusions show great heterogeneity.

Evidence base. Economic growth is a common concern of developed and developing countries. This section examines 20 empirical papers (involving nine countries) related to economic growth issues, which differ widely in their practical conclusions. Some studies argue that municipal mergers do not promote local economic growth. Hanes and Wikström (2008) explored the effect of Swedish municipal reforms on income growth in 1952 and found that mergers had no significant impact on average income growth. Savitch et al. (2010) studied the case of the Louisville and Jefferson County merger in the United States in 2003. They found no significant increase in per capita income, employment, and the number of business establishments after the merger. Hanes and Wikström (2010) use ordinary least squares regression to study Sweden's 1952 reforms and find no effect of mergers on income growth. Allers and Geertsema (2016) found that municipal mergers in the Netherlands had no impact on per capita property tax revenues based on a difference-in-differences model. Steiner and Kaiser (2017), based on data from two combined surveys of all local secretaries (senior civil servants) in Switzerland in 1998 and 2009, found that merger reforms did not result in a significant improvement or deterioration in local finances. Dollery and Ting (2017) studied municipal mergers in New South Wales (Australia) in 2004. They found that the government's financial sustainability ten years after the merger was much lower than that of a control group selected based on cluster analysis. Wallace and Dollery (2018) and Wallace and Dollery (2019), based on Australian case studies of Barraba and Manilla, respectively, show that mergers do not promote social and economic development. Matti and Neto (2022) use county-level data from 13 U.S. states and find that municipal mergers do not promote stabilization in employment, unemployment, per capita income, or the number of businesses.

Some studies suggest that municipal mergers promote local economic development. Hansen et al. (2014) used a difference-in-differences model to study the impact of municipal mergers in Denmark in 2007 and found that mergers improved the financial position of municipalities over five years. Tang and Hewings (2017) used a difference-in-differences model to analyze the impact of China's city-county merger reform on regional per capita GDP. They found that mergers significantly promoted the development of local economies, and the size of the promotion depends on local endowments related to aggregation. Tian et al. (2020) used a difference-in-differences model to analyze the impact of municipal mergers on the market price of second-hand housing in Fuyang County (China). They found that municipal mergers hindered an increase of housing prices in Fuyang in the short term but boosted housing prices in Fuyang in the long run. Yu and Hou (2021) used a difference-in-differences model to study the merger of two municipal districts in Shanghai. They found that the merger reform could promote a 1.6% increase in the real estate value of the two regions after the merger. Lowatcharin et al. (2021) compared the policy effects of municipal mergers in the United States and Thailand and found that mergers can have positive fiscal impacts. Zhang et al. (2022), based on the monthly housing price data of China's districts (counties) from 2010 to 2019, found that the merger of cities and counties significantly improved the house price correlation between the merged counties and urban communities. Egger et al. (2022) used nighttime light data as a proxy for economic activity, used a difference-in-differences model to analyze the effects of large-scale municipal mergers in Germany on local economic activities, and found that mergers would promote an increase in average lights. Heterogeneity analysis showed that consolidation increased nighttime lights in the local authorities of the absorbing partner but decreased nighttime glow in the absorbing regions. Yuan et al. (2022), based on data from Chinese listed companies from 1998 to 2018, used a difference-in-differences model to analyze the impact of municipal

mergers on the linkages between regional enterprises, and the results showed that mergers significantly promoted the stock price linkage between enterprises in different regions. Xu et al. (2022) used a difference-in-differences model based on a database of Chinese industrial enterprises from 1999 to 2006 and found that municipal mergers promoted the motivation of enterprises to use earnings management.

A few studies showed heterogeneous results. Hall et al. (2020) used synthetic controls to analyze city-county mergers in Lafayette-Lafayette Parish (Louisiana), Athens-Clark County (Georgia), and Augusta-Richmond County (Georgia). They found that the merger positively impacted the development of Lafayette Parish, which may have benefited from the advancement of regional development programs and improved government coordination. However, the merger hurt the economic growth of the other two cities.

Summary. Based on the above analysis, municipal mergers cannot promote economic growth in most western countries. In contrast, in developing countries, municipal mergers are usually used as a policy tool to promote economic development. We will discuss it in Section 5.

4.1.4 Population migration

Assumptions. This section will discuss population migration, an important factor in economic growth. The impact of municipal amalgamation on population growth is also a classic issue. After the merger, improvements in public goods and infrastructure supply in smaller cities affected population growth due to the free-rider effect. Besides, diseconomies of scale, such as housing pressure in core cities, will also promote population migration (Kauder, 2016). However, some studies also observe that municipal mergers may deprive surrounding areas of opportunities to engage in a series of economic activities, affect employment opportunities in small cities, and adversely affect the population of small cities (Suzuki and Sakuwa, 2016). Therefore, the impact of municipal mergers on population migration is uncertain.

Evidence base. This section examines five empirical papers (involving four countries) on population migration. Hanes and Wikström (2008) explored the effect of municipal mergers in Sweden on population growth in 1952. They found that mergers positively affected population growth for cities with smaller populations, possibly because merger reforms reduced the rate of out-migration in merged cities. Except for cities with smaller populations, mergers will not help maintain local population levels. Hanes and Wikström (2010) used ordinary least squares regression to study Sweden's 1952 reforms and found that mergers positively affected population growth in smaller cities and that voluntary municipalities had higher population growth rates. Kauder (2016) used the PSM model to study the impact of municipal mergers in Germany and found that mergers promoted the population growth of small municipalities by about 47% but had no significant effect on large municipalities. Suzuki and Sakuwa (2016) used the PSM model to find that Japanese city-county mergers do not affect the local population growth of all original cities within each merged group equally. Municipal mergers can hurt population growth if the municipality is not the largest city among the merger partners. There is no evidence that municipal consolidation has positively or negatively impacted population growth in the largest cities. Karlsson and Eythórssón (2019) used a fixed-effects panel model to analyze the impact of municipal mergers on population migration in Iceland. The study found that urban mergers with different population sizes hurt the net migration

of the 16-74-year-old population. Still, if two or five municipalities merge, it can be observed that the merger promotes net migration.

Summary. Most studies observe that municipal mergers promote the increase in the population size of small cities but have no significant impact on large cities. However, evidence from Japan suggests that municipal consolidation is detrimental to population growth in smaller cities.

4.2 Democratic effect

We define the democratic effect as the impact of municipal mergers on electoral activity (voter turnout, councilor representation), legislative activity, and citizens' sense of place identity and satisfaction. Democratic effects have been a concern for municipal consolidation reform, especially as opponents often cite it as a reason to resist it. Political participation can effectively measure the democratic effect. Thus, several studies use election activities as an indicator to observe the democratic effect of municipal mergers. In this chapter, we focus on the empirical analysis of municipal mergers on electoral activity. In addition, we also analyze the effects of the merger reform on legislative activity and citizen attitudes.

4.2.1 Election campaign

Assumptions. Municipal mergers often reduce citizens' enthusiasm for voting in elections. Municipal mergers expand jurisdictions, making voters feel more disconnected from politicians (Van Houwelingen, 2017). On the one hand, more residents will be contacted by councilors; on the other hand, the physical distance of residents from the city hall will also increase (Dahl & Tufte, 1973). In addition, when a small city is merged with a large city, the representatives of the new city council are more biased towards the large town, which may cause a problem of representational imbalance (Jakobsen & Kjaer, 2016). In conclusion, municipal mergers are considered to hurt local elections.

Evidence base. This section examines 19 empirical papers (involving 12 countries) related to electoral issues that differ in their practical conclusions. Most studies have concluded that municipal mergers are not conducive to electoral activities. Based on the national level, Shimizu (2012) introduced that the reform of municipal mergers in Japan created more robust and independent places with politicians and voters farther away from national parties. Horiuchi et al. (2015) similarly found that municipal merger reform in Japan significantly reduced voter turnout and gained a smaller share of votes for the ruling party in national elections. Jakobsen and Kjaer (2016) examine political representation and geographic bias in the new government following the merger of municipalities in Denmark and find that the struggle for representation in the new government is influenced by center-periphery relations created by the relative size of the former jurisdictions. Van Houwelingen's (2017) study based on Dutch municipal mergers shows that population size hurts local political participation. Greater physical and mental distance between voters and politicians appears to be a significant reason for the decline in local political interest and involvement after municipal mergers. An empirical study in Switzerland by Koch and Rochat (2017) shows that municipal mergers reduce voter turnout and that this inhibitory effect is more potent in smaller cities. Additionally, turnout declined mainly in the first post-merger election and to a lesser extent in subsequent elections. Roesel (2017) analyzed the effect of municipal mergers in the German state

of Saxony on electoral voting using a synthetic control method and found that mergers reduced voter turnout in regional elections and increased the vote share of populist right-wing parties. Rodrigues and Meza (2018) used a difference-in-differences model to study municipal mergers in Portugal and found that mergers hurt election turnout, especially in rural local governments. Zeedan (2017) used ordinary least squares regression to see that Israel's 2003 merger reforms significantly reduced voter turnout and parliamentary representation. This negative effect is more pronounced in large areas (more than 20,000 inhabitants). Heinisch et al. (2018) studied the impact of municipal mergers in the Austrian state of Styria and found that merger reforms reduced election turnout between 2010 and 2015.

An empirical analysis of Germany and Austria by Blesse and Roesel (2019) shows that municipal mergers lead to a persistent decline in voter turnout, with right-wing populists appearing to gain additional support. Wallace and Dollery (2019), based on a case study of Manilla (Australia), showed that survey participants were dissatisfied with the political representation their communities received in a merged parliament. Yamada and Arai (2021) investigated the impact of municipal mergers on politicians-voter relations in Japan through a questionnaire. They found that voters in small cities experiencing mergers interacted less frequently with politicians and had a lower favorable opinion of politicians than before the merger. Harjunen et al. (2021) used a difference-in-differences model to study municipal mergers in Finland and found that mergers resulted in a highly unequal geopolitical representation of the merged municipalities in councils. Small and politically marginalized cities saw significant reductions in local public positions in administrative, health, and social care services. Allers et al. (2021) used a difference-in-differences model to study the effect of municipal mergers on voter turnout in the Netherlands and found that municipal mergers reduced turnout by 2.2 percentage points in local elections and 0.7 percentage points in national polls. A U.S.-based study by Acuff (2021) found that the coalition of city and county governments did lead to a significant year-over-year decline in African-American representation.

A few studies suggest that municipal mergers' effect on local elections is conditional. A survey by Lapointe et al. (2018) using the difference-in-differences method of municipal mergers in Finland showed that voter turnout was four percentage points lower in smaller cities compared to similar cities that did not merge. Nevertheless, relatively large cities saw little change in turnout.

A handful of studies argue that municipal mergers do not harm local elections. Steiner and Kaiser (2017), based on data from two combined surveys of all local secretaries (senior civil servants) in Switzerland in 1998 and 2009, found that the effect of merger reform on the number of administrative staff was insignificant. After the merger, local autonomy was strengthened, and citizens' interest in local politics increased slightly. However, the authors argue that testing citizens' political interests by asking government representatives may be biased because civil servants do not know precisely what citizens' attitudes are but base their perceptions on their observations. Bhatti and Hansen (2019) used a first-difference model to find that Denmark's 2007 municipal merger reform positively impacted voter turnout in the short run, which may be election efforts. At the same time, the study found no clear evidence that mergers had a negative mid- to long-term impact on turnout. Lowatcharin et al. (2021) analyzed the policy effects of municipal mergers in the United States and Thailand and found that mergers negatively impacted democratic participation. The author believes that the excellent foundation of democratic participation before the merger and the still small size of the city after the merger are possible explanations.

Summary. In summary, the prevailing view is that municipal mergers harm the electoral activities of merged local governments, usually due to the increased physical and mental distance between voters and politicians. Furthermore, municipal mergers can also create an imbalance in the representation of political participation in different communities.

4.2.2 Parliamentary officers and legislation, local identity and citizen satisfaction

Assumptions. Based on the expansion of jurisdictions and the contradictions between different original governments, municipal mergers have negatively affected local officials, legislative activity, and residents' attitudes.

Evidence base. This section discusses other democratic effects of municipal mergers, including parliamentary officials and legislation and citizens' local identity and satisfaction, examining nine literature (involving four countries). Kjær et al. (2010) studied the impact of Danish merger reform on the functioning of local councils. They found that mergers resulted in parliamentarians seeing themselves as less influential than those in unchanged municipalities and prompted a shift in the influence of local polity to the executive branch (from local politicians to administrators). Takagishi et al. (2012) used structural equation modeling to study the psychological pressure of municipal mergers in Japan on local government employees, arguing that the loss of work value brings more significant psychological stress than the increase in external workload. Suzuki and Ha (2018) studied the impact of municipal mergers on local legislative activities in Japan and found that municipal mergers were negatively correlated with legislative performance. Mergers hinder the implementation of legislative action, and local councils that experience municipal mergers propose fewer municipal bylaws.

Lassen and Serritzlew (2011) used a difference-in-differences model to study the impact of municipal mergers in Denmark in 2007 and found that mergers reduced the internal political effectiveness of local governments; that is, citizens' confidence in municipal authorities declined. Hansen (2013), also based on Denmark's 2007 reforms, found that mergers reduced citizens' trust in the government. Alexander (2013), based on an Australian questionnaire, shows that residents are still strongly dissatisfied with forced mergers. It is widely believed that the coalition has weakened the functioning of local government across the city and has largely failed to effectively reconcile the interests of the various towns and communities following the merger. Soguel and Silberstein (2015) used the conditional valuation method to analyze the impact of Swiss municipal mergers on citizens' local identity, and the results showed that mergers weakened local identity. Hansen (2015) analyzed data from public opinion surveys after the merger of Danish municipalities and found that as population size increased, citizens' satisfaction with local services, local democracy, and how they dealt with problems decreased. Hansen and Kjaer (2020) studied the effect of municipal mergers in Denmark on residents' emotional attachment. They found that when smaller municipalities merged with larger ones, citizens living in smaller cities were less territorially attached; citizens living in larger municipalities were not.

Summary. The above research shows that municipal mergers adversely affect local council operations, officials' psychological pressure, and legislative activities, weakening residents' emotional attachment and satisfaction with their hometowns. In the future, these factors should be considered when formulating municipal consolidation policies.

4.3 Management effect

The management effect in this paper refers to the impact of municipal mergers on local government management capabilities, including the level of public services provided by local governments in the traditional sense, administrative efficiency, and management capabilities on watersheds, the environment, and energy. In the following, we will discuss it in two parts.

4.3.1 Public service and administrative efficiency

Assumptions. Municipal mergers expand the scope of jurisdictions. Larger jurisdictions may be less responsive to the needs and preferences of communities within their boundaries (Dollery, 2010). Especially those small cities that lost political power in elections can perceive a decline in the level of public services after mergers (Yamada, 2018). Since there is no clear evidence that municipal mergers reduce government expenditures, and the level of public services has not improved significantly, municipal mergers are generally not considered to improve local government efficiency.

Evidence base. Public service and administrative efficiency can reflect the management capabilities of local governments. This section examines 11 related papers (involving eight countries). It is generally believed that municipal mergers will not significantly improve the level of public services. Allers and Geertsema (2016) used house price increases as a proxy variable to support the improvement of public services. Based on a difference-in-differences model, they found that the merger of Dutch municipalities would not increase house prices; that is, it did not improve public services. Foged (2016) used Denmark's 2007 municipal mergers as a quasi-natural experiment to study the relationship between population size and service outsourcing. He found that mergers favored service outsourcing that was difficult to measure or regulated by free-choice markets and was not conducive to high fixed-cost service outsourcing. Krøtel et al. (2017) found that Denmark's municipal merger reform did not affect public management related to daily operations based on a difference-in-differences model but positively impacted general management related to overall tasks such as creating a vision, serving the mayor, and maintaining external relations. Steiner and Kaiser (2017), based on data from two combined surveys of all local secretaries (senior civil servants) in Switzerland in 1998 and 2009, found that the quality of public service delivery would improve after the merger. Nevertheless, the author said this might be related to good self-evaluations of officials. Lowatcharin et al. (2021) compared and analyzed the policy effects of municipal mergers in the United States and Thailand and found that mergers can positively impact public services. Nevertheless, this conclusion is based on descriptive analysis rather than rigorous econometric analysis. Yamada (2018), through a questionnaire survey of municipal mergers in Japan, found that the perceived level of public services within merged communities declined more than those that remained unchanged. A study in Denmark by Blom-Hansen et al. (2021) showed that municipal consolidation did not affect the effectiveness of public schools.

Generally, it is believed that municipal mergers do not improve administrative efficiency. Haneda et al. (2012) used the DEA model to measure administrative efficiency and found that the municipal merger reform in Ibaraki (Japan) did not improve administrative efficiency. Based on Dutch research, Allers and Van Ommeren (2016) found that municipal mergers do not reduce administrative efficiency, but inter-municipal cooperation may decrease. Pevcin (2017) estimated

the technical efficiency of Slovenian cities using a DEA model and found that mergers can only bring economies of scale and efficiency gains to tiny towns. McQuestin et al. (2018) used a DEA model to estimate urban administrative efficiency in Queensland (Australia) and found that the expected improvement in technical efficiency from mergers failed to materialize, which may be attributable to increased personnel expenditures.

Summary. Most studies found that municipal mergers will not improve the level of public services and the administrative efficiency of local governments. Only a few studies have concluded that municipal consolidation can enhance the level of non-routine public services and the organizational efficiency of small cities.

4.3.2 Environment and land management

Assumptions. In this section, the environmental management effect mainly refers to the local government's investment in environmental governance or changes in environmental indicators. The land management effect relates primarily to the management of urban construction land. Compared with other issues, research on the impact of municipal mergers on the environment and land started relatively late, and there are not many related empirical analyzes. In existing studies, municipal mergers positively affect the environment and land by reducing vicious competition among local governments and regional integration (Li et al., 2021).

Evidence base. In recent years, research on the management effects of municipal mergers has expanded to other topics. This section reviews seven empirical pieces of literature (involving two countries) covering environmental governance costs, environmental index, and urban land use. Mizunoya et al. (2021) used an input-output model to analyze the impact of municipal mergers on watershed environmental governance budgets in Japan. They found that municipal mergers can significantly reduce the funding required to improve the water environment. Li et al. (2021) used a difference-in-differences model to find that China's city-county consolidation policy is beneficial to reducing urban energy intensity. The policy effect only began to appear in the third year after implementation. Feng et al. (2022) used a geo-detector model to find that administrative division adjustment reforms reduced the PM 2.5 index of Chinese urban agglomerations during 2009-2017. Cao et al. (2022) used a difference-in-differences model to find that the merger of cities and counties in China significantly reduced the environmental pollution of the merged cities. Feng and Wang (2021, 2022) used a geo-detector model to find that the reform of municipal mergers in China significantly promoted urban expansion.

Summary. We find that concerns about environmental governance and land use exist mainly in developing countries. Empirical studies have shown that municipal mergers can effectively reduce the budget needed to improve the water environment, urban energy intensity, and pollution levels. This improvement effect is related to regional integration effects, collaborative governance, and improved intergovernmental relations.

5 Possible reasons for controversy and understanding of the methodology

In this section, we analyze the possible reasons for the divergence of current empirical conclusions on some main topics and discuss methodological issues. In the field of economic effects, the number of practical articles on the impact of local government spending is the largest, and empirical analysis based on different countries shows different results. When implementing merger policies, different countries face different degrees of political competition consumption, internalization of local public goods supply spillovers, and increased heterogeneity of preferences in merged cities. All of these reasons will bring a specific cost to the scale economy effect, which will affect the direction and significance of the coefficients of the analysis results. From the conditional analysis of the existing literature, the urban population size (Hanes, 2015), population density (Edwards & Xiao, 2009), the relationship between the merged areas (Hanes, 2015), expenditure categories (Andrews, 2015; Moio & Uusitalo, 2013), and observation time (McQuestin et al., 2022; Miyazaki, 2018) will significantly impact the expenditure reduction effect caused by the merger. Considering these conditions that may result from mergers and affect local government spending should be the focus of policymakers when formulating merger policies in the region.

It is a mainstream conclusion that municipal mergers can expand the common pool size compared with local government spending. Empirical analysis based on different countries shows that the population size of the initial region relative to the new area (Hinnerich, 2009), the city's relationship at the time of the merger (Hirota & Yunoue, 2020; Hirota & Yunoue, 2017), officer's cognition (Askim & Houlberg, 2022; Hansen, 2019), the number of merged cities (Fritz & Feld, 2020; Hansen, 2014), social norms and regulatory measures (Goto et al., 2020; Nakazawa, 2018) all have an impact on the size of the common pool, especially the research based on the merger of municipalities in South Africa (Goto et al., 2020) observes that the occurrence of common pool problems can be effectively prevented using monitoring.

Economic growth is also a topic of focus in studies on the impact of municipal mergers. Judging from the conclusions of the existing empirical literature, the empirical research conclusions between different countries or within the same country are different. The reasons for the difference are as follows. First, the selection of dependent variables is diverse (Matti & Neto, 2022; Tang & Hewings, 2017). For example, research in Western countries focuses on the analysis of employment and per capita income, while research in China prefers to use per capita GDP as a dependent variable. Second, the research methods differ (Lowatcharin et al., 2021; Wallace & Dollery, 2018; Hansen et al., 2014). Economic growth includes several research methods, including descriptive analysis, case analysis, questionnaire survey, interview, cluster analysis, difference-in-differences model, and synthetic control method. The difference in the degree of identification of the causal relationship between each technique may lead to different consequences. Third, the institutional environment is different (Tang & Hewings, 2017; Hansen et al., 2014). For example, as a developing country, government officials have always valued China's GDP growth, which is different from that of western developed countries. These differences are all aspects that should be considered when assessing the economic performance of municipal mergers.

Voter voting and political representation have been classic issues in the field of democratic

effects. The prevailing view is that municipal mergers reduce voter turnout, and the effect is more potent in smaller cities. Because the expansion of the size of the town after the merger has opened the mental and physical distance between voters and politicians (van Houwelingen, 2017). A few studies hold that municipal mergers will not reduce citizens' political participation. The authors' explanations include the following: (1) the research data comes from the subjective assessments of politicians (Steiner & Kaiser, 2017), (2) there is already a good foundation for political involvement before mergers (Lowatcharin et al., 2021), and (3) the size of cities after mergers is still relatively small (Lowatcharin et al., 2021). Regarding the issue of political representation, some studies have suggested that mergers will lead to imbalances in parliamentary political representation across regions (Acuff, 2021; Harjunen et al., 2021). In the field of management effects, there have been differences in the impact of municipal mergers on public services. Possible reasons include: (1) whether the interview data has a personal standpoint (Steiner & Kaiser, 2017), (2) the degree of identification of causality by the research method (Yamada, 2018; Krøtel et al., 2017).

Regarding methodology, we find that the current research trend is increasingly focusing on identifying causal relationships, from the initial descriptive analysis and ordinary least squares model to the existing difference-in-differences model, synthetic control model, and instrumental variable model. However, there are still differences in the degree of identification of causality on different issues. On classic topics such as local government expenditure and the common pool, most studies have adopted the difference-in-differences model and focused on analyzing endogenous problems (McQuestin et al., 2022; Pickering et al., 2022; Goto et al., 2020; Fritz & Feld, 2020). On the issue of economic growth, empirical methods are more diverse, including methods such as descriptive analysis (Wallace & Dollery, 2019), questionnaire surveys (Wallace & Dollery, 2018), interviews (Wallace & Dollery, 2018), spatial econometric models (Matti & Neto, 2022), difference-in-differences models (Egger et al., 2021), and synthetic control methods (Hall et al., 2020). On some topics in the democracy and governance effects, many studies only use descriptive analysis. Most of these studies are based on questionnaires or interviews (Lowatcharin et al., 2021; Aulich et al., 2014; Alexander, 2013), which are challenging to meet the conditions of panel data, limiting the use of methods such as the difference-in-differences. In recent years, such issues as the environment, housing prices, and enterprise development have adopted a more rigorous difference-in-differences model to identify causal relationships.

Furthermore, as one of the most widely used measurement methods today, it is necessary to highlight the latest trends in the difference-in-differences model. Municipal merger reforms in most countries are gradual; that is, the implementation of policies is usually not completed within a year. Recent literature has shown that when the policy is implemented gradually, the estimated coefficients derived from the two-way fixed-effects estimator can have adverse severe weight problems if there is significant heterogeneity of individual treatment effects (De Chaisemartin & D'Haultfoeuille, 2020; Sant'Anna & Zhao, 2020; Goodman-Bacon, 2021), which may lead to serious estimation bias. In the future, it is essential to improve the traditional fixed-effect double-difference model and explore new causality identification methods.

6 Discussion and future research

Municipal merger policy has always been widely valued by governments and society and practiced in countries worldwide. From the perspective of published literature, although the number of papers published has increased in recent years, the total amount is still small, especially due to the lack of

empirical research. This systematic literature review analyzes the existing empirical papers on the impact assessment of municipal mergers and sorts out the existing research growth trends, case distribution, research areas, consensus and controversies in research conclusions, and methodology. It attempts to propose the possible reasons for the existence of controversies. This will have particular reference significance for the decision-making reference of local governments.

We draw three main conclusions from a review of the 89 selected empirical papers.

Research trends. The number of research papers on municipal mergers is increasing, most of which are in Western developed countries and Japan. In contrast, research in developing countries is mainly found in China. Research on municipal mergers in developed countries focuses on local government spending, common pools, economic growth, public services, administrative efficiency, and citizens' political participation and satisfaction. In developing countries, they pay more attention to economic growth, environmental governance, and land use. This reflects the differentiated policy goals of developed and developing countries when implementing municipal mergers.

Mainstream views. *In terms of economic effects*, most studies observe that although municipal mergers will significantly reduce administrative expenditures, they will not significantly reduce the total expenditure of local governments. On the one hand, many local government expenditure items are labor-intensive and are usually more efficient on a smaller scale; on the other hand, massive scales can also produce diseconomies of scale. Existing direct studies on municipal mergers do not give an optimal population size because the threshold of economies of scale in different countries is affected by various factors such as geographical environment, political system, level of economic development, and implementation process of merger policies. For the implementation process of mergers, the impact of compulsory and voluntary mergers on local government expenditures has opposite conclusions, and more empirical tests are still needed. On the common pool, most of the existing studies observe that municipal mergers will generate a common pool, and the increase in the number of merged governments will promote the expansion of the same collection. However, social norms and corresponding regulatory measures can effectively control the common pool problem. Municipal mergers cannot promote economic growth in most western countries but have a positive effect in developing countries. *In terms of democratic effects*, municipal mergers have significant adverse effects. On the one hand, the expansion of jurisdictions alienates the spiritual and physical distance between voters and politicians, and voters have a lower sense of local identity; on the other hand, it becomes more difficult for governments in large jurisdictions to satisfy heterogeneous preferences. Regarding electoral representativeness, we must pay special attention to the merger of large and small cities. After the merger, the large cities will take the lead, quickly reducing small towns to the periphery and subsidiary of large cities. Research by Bhatti and Hansen (2019) reminds us that turnout increases during the early stages of mergers may be due to electoral efforts by old municipalities to secure influence in new cities. *In terms of management effects*, municipal mergers usually do not improve public services and administrative efficiency but make efforts to create a vision, serve the mayor, and maintain external relations. Furthermore, recent studies have also found that municipal mergers positively affect environmental protection, energy conservation, and construction land expansion.

Possible sources of controversy and methodology. Some research topics draw entirely different conclusions in various empirical articles. Analysis shows that this difference may be caused by

policy implementation background, data validity, variable selection, and research methods. The current empirical research has transformed from simple descriptive analysis to regression analysis. With the development of research methods and data availability, empirical research in recent years has given more consideration to endogenous issues and adopted more complex econometric models, such as DID model, synthetic control method and structural equation model, etc. However, this methodological progress varies across different topics, and some studies using interview and questionnaire data lack rigorous causal identification.

As mentioned above, today's central and local governments are still highly enthusiastic about municipal mergers, and our existing empirical research is still relatively lacking. In particular, some contradictory and ambiguous conclusions cannot provide a good reference for formulating relevant policies. Here, we propose the following three suggestions for future municipal merger reforms:

The central government. In most countries, municipal consolidation is usually a top-down process. The central government is not only the promoter of reform but also the supervisor of the reform process. Studies have shown that the central government can control and avoid the common pool problem through effective regulation and legislation. Additionally, the central government needs to consider more alternatives to municipal consolidation reform. Generally, municipal merger policies face relatively high economic and political costs, risks, and disputes. Existing empirical studies mostly observe that mergers have damaged the political participation of local citizens and have questioned the economies of scale brought about by mergers, which has also become a reason for opponents. The choice of cooperation between cities and the establishment of a particular zone government can be regarded as a more powerful means. Given the significant impact of global events represented by Covid-19 on people's lives, people have begun to re-examine the pros and cons of big government and the distribution of urban scale. The central government should approach merger reform more cautiously.

Local government. The local government is the main body of the municipal merger and the specific maker of the merger plan. Local governments should realize that not all services in big cities have the potential for economies of scale. Capital-intensive services represented by urban infrastructure have good potential for economies of scale. In contrast, labor-intensive services directly related to citizens usually do not have the potential for economies of scale. The formulation of the merger plan should be based on the scientific understanding of the problems in the city itself. Furthermore, most studies show that mergers among many small cities have a greater probability of achieving economies of scale, avoiding "exploitation of the great by the small" and electoral representational imbalances than mergers between large and small cities.

Research scholar. Future researchers need to standardize the research paradigm of empirical papers, including using precise and reliable research data, representative research variables, and selecting rigorous and diverse methods to identify the causal effects of policies. However, it seems that the appropriate research methods are limited at present. This needs to be further expanded for classical methods such as DID model and synthetic control method.

Researchers should combine the economic effects, democratic effects, and management effects of municipal mergers to comprehensively evaluate the benefits and risks of municipal merger policies. When the existing literature studies local government expenditure or public services, most of them are considered separately. Few studies directly examine municipal mergers' impact on urban

administrative efficiency. However, more are indirect assessments, that is, the policy is the background rather than a variable, such as examining the effects of population size on public services in the context of combined policies (D'Inverno et al., 2020). Further, we see little research on combined effects, where economic and democratic effects are usually assessed separately. In this regard, new comprehensive indicators and efficiency analysis methods (D'Inverno & De Witte, 2020) are important in evaluating future municipal mergers' complete effects.

Also, international comparative research should be strengthened. Currently, most international studies on the impact of municipal mergers are in developed countries, and there are relatively few evaluation cases in developing countries. Since the implementation of municipal merger policy goals in various countries is affected by various factors such as political system, development orientation, social culture, and geographical environment, strengthening international comparative research will help deepen the understanding of existing literature research conclusions in different countries and also help to find potential explanations for different findings on the same research topic.

The purpose of the present paper is not to give a unified, definite, and definitive conclusion on the impact of municipal mergers. Due to the differences in local government functions, legal systems, political systems, and economic bases in different countries, municipal mergers may produce different effects. This paper aims to sort out the current research progress of municipal merger policy and the possible conditional effects of different research conclusions through comparative research. We hope this can provide more consideration for local governments when formulating their policies.

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Appendix

Figure 2 presents the papers (219) we searched in this literature review related to the topic of municipal mergers and selected empirical papers (89) on the impact of municipal mergers. We found an upward trend in the number of publications on municipal mergers and empirical performance analysis papers, especially after 2017, which showed that the research on municipal mergers is not outdated and is gaining more and more attention. A possible explanation for this research trend is that policy orientation drives research demand. More than 5,000 municipalities were reduced due to municipal mergers in only 15 European countries from 2008 to 2017 (Swianiewicz, 2018), which provided rich cases for empirical research and prompted scholars to eagerly draw conclusions through empirical analysis to provide a scientific basis for local government decision-making. Considering that the existing literature has not reached a unified understanding of the effect of municipal mergers, the strong controversy between policy opponents and supporters, and the rapid increase in empirical literature in recent years (the number of publications in the past three years accounted for 31.46% of the total publications), it is necessary to carry out this literature review.

Fig.2 Municipal merger papers

Table 1 shows that the current empirical analysis literature mainly focuses on the following three types of research areas: economic effects, democratic effects, and management effects. In particular, research in recent years has expanded from the classic issues (like local government spending, common pool, and political participation) to focus on areas such as the environment, energy, and land use, reflecting the diversification of impact assessments for municipal mergers. We noticed that these new issues are usually of more concern to developing countries because, with the rapid growth of the urban economy, local governments in developing countries are concerned about environmental pollution, energy consumption, and land resource utilization.

Topics of economic effects include local government spending, common pools, economic growth, and population migration. Regarding the case distribution of economic effects, most research cases occurred in developed countries, with Sweden (8), Australia (7), Germany (6), and Japan (6) being the most numerous, and the developing countries only include China (7), South Africa (1), and Thailand (1). Topics in democratic effects include electoral activity, parliamentary officials and legislation, local identity, and civic satisfaction. The research cases are mainly from developed countries such as Denmark (7), Japan (5), and Switzerland (3). Topics in the management effects include public services, administrative efficiency, environment, and land management. The research cases mainly occurred in China (6), Denmark (3), and Japan (3). From a method perspective,

the DID model is the most widely used in all research topics. The synthetic control method, DEA model, panel regression model, OLS model, questionnaire surveys, and interviews are standard research methods for municipal merger performance evaluation.

Table 1. Classification of empirical literature

Research area	Specific topics	Main research methods	Country (paper number)
economic effects	local government spending	DID, synthetic control method, PSM, OLS, IV, case study, interview	Australia (4), Germany (3), Japan (2), Sweden (2), Finland (2), United States (1), United Kingdom (1), Netherlands (1), Denmark (1), Austria (1), Canada (1), Israel (1)
	common pool	DID, PSM-DID, logistic regression, OLS	Japan (3), Denmark (3), Sweden (2), Germany (1), Finland (1), Norway (1), South Africa (1)
	economic growth	DID, synthetic control method, OLS, descriptive analysis, cluster analysis, spatial econometric model, survival analysis model, case study, questionnaire, interview	China (7), United States (4), Australia (3), Sweden (2), Germany (1), Netherlands (1), Denmark (1), Switzerland (1), Thailand (1)
	population migration	panel regression model, OLS, PSM	Sweden (2), Iceland (1), Germany (1), Japan (1)
democratic effects	election campaign	DID, synthetic control method, OLS, panel regression model, descriptive analysis, case study, questionnaire, interview	Japan (3), United States (2), Switzerland (2), Germany (2), Austria (2), Denmark (2), Netherlands (2), Finland (2), Portugal (1), Israel (1), Australia (1), Thailand (1)
	parliamentary officials and legislation	DID, panel regression model, structural equation modeling	Japan (2), Denmark (1)
	local identity	DID, conditional valuation	Denmark (1), Switzerland (1)
	citizen satisfaction	DID, questionnaire	Denmark (3), Australia (1)
management effects	public service	DID, descriptive analysis, questionnaire, case study	Denmark (3), United States (1), Netherlands (1), Switzerland (1), Japan (1), Thailand (1)
	administrative efficiency	DEA, OLS	Australia (1), Netherlands (1), Japan (1), Slovenia (1)
	environment and land management	DID, survival analysis model, geodetector, input-output model	China (6), Japan (1)